

ECOLOGICAL JUSTICE: FROM SACRED GROVES TO ENVIRONMENTAL LITIGATION

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Paper Received On: 20 NOVEMBER 2025

Peer Reviewed On: 24 DECEMBER 2025

Published On: 01 JANUARY 2026

Abstract

India is a land earmarked by pluralistic religious practices, rituals, and customs which has shaped deep cultural and spiritual diversity. A closer examination reveals not only India but across the World diverse religions, customs, traditions, and practices exists, which have historically contributed to the preservation of the natural environment. The community-based conservation, taboos, Sacred Groves are few examples how such customs, traditions and practices have played a significant role in ensuring biodiversity conservation and ecological balance. Over the past few decades, the unsustainable exploitation of natural resources without proper preservation has led to significant environmental degradation which has resulted in a range of natural disasters including earthquakes, floods, tsunamis, wildfires, and volcanic eruptions, contributing to intensified global warming and climate-related risks. The ongoing environmental crises have ignited judicial activism in environment protection. The judiciary has played a significant role by evolving through its landmark judgements increasingly recognizing and reinforcing not only environmental justice but also strengthening the framework of ecological justice. The judiciary is holistically integrating while deciding environmental matters as now it is inevitable for the judiciary to not only protect human rights vis-à-vis environment but also protecting the whole eco-system. While the judiciary cannot work in isolation, a comprehensive study involving all stakeholders is essential. This includes environment scientist, conservationists, geologists, and such other experts who study about the environment alongside the traditional knowledge of tribal communities and the expertise of religious scholars who has the knowledge of Sacred Groves and forest. It is therefore, essential to evaluate the scaredness of such groves and their contribution in preserving the ecology which will enable to frame and decide effective environmental laws and related matters. This paper is an attempt to briefly understand about the Sacred Groves and its cultural and ecological significance and an overview of landmark environmental litigation to date.

Keywords: *Ecological Justice, Sacred Grove, Environment litigation, Conservation, T. N. Godavarman Thirumulpad.*

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Introduction: As the world evolves, there is a growing awareness among people about the importance of preserving the environment. This realisation, however, has come late due to the incessant deforestation and its numerous other adverse environmental hazards, which have led to severe global warming issues and other environmental disasters. Environmentalists, activists, and the judiciary play a significant role in protecting the environment. One such notable case is *T. N. Godavarman Thirumalpad v. Union of India (1995)*² and has broadly interpreted the term “forest” and emphasised the significance of preserving Sacred Groves (Authority, 2025). Before analysing briefly this judgement, it is imperative to understand the meaning of “Ecological Justice” and “Sacred Grove” and to understand the journey so far of ‘environment litigation’ to ‘ecological justice’.

Rationale of the Study: Primarily, it is imperative for the judiciary and legal fraternity, while dealing with environmental cases, to involve experts such as environmental scientists, conservationists, ecologists, and relevant contributors to gain a holistic perspective and enable them to provide ecological justice. Research on the Sacred Grove is in its early stages, and there is a notable lack of awareness. Accordingly, all stakeholders such as, the government, judiciary, academicians, and ecologists, need to study the ecological and cultural significance of the Sacred Grove, necessarily involving the tribals, indigenous groups, and protectors of the Sacred Grove.

Objectives: The objectives of this paper are as follows:

1. To emphasise the importance of ecological justice rather than considering it as mere environmental litigation.
2. To unearth, to a certain extent, the cultural and ecological significance of Sacred Groves.

Research Methodology: Primarily, this research is based on the doctrinal approach through available sources. The primary sources referred to are the statutes, holy scriptures and judgments. The secondary sources relied upon are the commentaries, journals, articles, and other relevant authorities.

Scope & Limitations: The scope of this paper is to highlight preservation of the environment from a holistic perspective, more particularly, the remaining rich flora and fauna of the Sacred Grove. The limitation of this research is the time constraint that restricts further study and investigation, which could have provided an impetus to understand the spiritual, cultural and

² In Re: T.N. Godavarman Thirumalpad (W.P. 202/1995)

ecological significance of the Sacred Grove and the clarity that brings in framing more effective laws of preservation.

Literature Review: An Extensive body of literature is available on the topic of environmental protection, conservation and laws. However, in this paper, the author is exploring law and aspects of the environment, particularly the Sacred Groves. There is, however, limited literature available on the Sacred Grove from a legal perspective. In this paper, the author has reviewed a book and an article below:

1. **Ecological Justice and the Extinction Crisis - Giving living beings their due:** The book by Anna Wienhues, which was published by Bristol University Press in 2020, is a critical analysis of the existing geo-political perspective on the environment, and the author provides a robust biodiversity framework, emphasising the importance of ecological justice (Wienhues, 2020).
2. **Sacred Groves and Conservation: The Comparative History of Tradition Reserves in the Mediterranean Area and in South India:** This article by authors M.D. Subash Chandran and J. Donald Hughes, published by The White Horse Press in the year 2000, in the Journal named “Environment and History”, explores the balance between humans and the ecosystem with the remaining Sacred Groves, particularly in Uttara Kannada (Hughes, 2000).

Significance of Sacred Groves: Since time immemorial, all over the World, people consider the planet Earth as “Mother Earth”, more particularly in India. This thought aligns with the sacred scriptures of Hinduism and the belief systems in Christianity, Buddhism, and Greek mythology (Kattukaran, 1993) and in many other religions.

Apropos, the Sacred Grove, the terms are self-explanatory; “Sacred”, which means “considered to be holy and deserving respect, especially because of a connection with a God” and “Grove” means “a group of trees planted close together” (Dictionary, n.d.). Sacred Grove, as defined by the Oxford Reference as “A stand (grove) of trees that is regarded as having spiritual value or meaning” (Oxford, n.d.). The presence of Sacred Grove is not restricted to India but exists all over the World in different forms, names, and cultures. In India itself, Sacred Groves have several names in different States, such as in Maharashtra as “*Devrai or Devgudi*”, in Kerala as “*Kaavu*”, in Rajasthan as “*Orans*”, in Karnataka as “*Devarakaadu*”, and so forth (Kannan CS Warriar, 2023). Sacred Groves also exist in Japan, North American tribes, West Africa, the Philippines, Nepal, Thailand, China and are spread across the World. These Sacred Groves are spiritually important and are revered as ancestral spirits or local deities (Ravi S. Copyright © 2025, *Scholarly Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies*

Behera, n.d.). It is pertinent to comprehensively examine from both socio-legal and spiritual dimensions, for it is the spiritual ethos that often inspires the societal values, later gaining legal acceptance. Therefore, it is necessary to explore the spiritual aspect of the sacred grove to understand and effectively implement ecological justice in full fervour.

Spiritually, the revered Bhagavat Gita, in its verse 26 of Chapter 10, states the following:

“अश्वत्थः सर्ववृक्षाणां देवर्षीणां च नारदः ।
गन्धर्वाणां चित्ररथः सिद्धानां कपिलो मुनिः ॥२६॥”
“*asvatthaḥ sarva-vṛkṣāṇām devarṣīṇām ca nāradaḥ
gandharvāṇām citrarathaḥ siddhānām kapilo muniḥ*”

This has been interpreted by spiritual and language scholars as “Among all trees, I am the Asvattha (the holy fig tree).....” (Kaushik, 1994). This verse itself proves the spiritual significance of the trees and the surrounding nature. Even in Buddhism, Lord Gautam Buddha attained enlightenment under a Bodhi Tree³ (Premarathna, 2025). Bodhi Tree is also known as the Sacred Fig. Similarly, groups of trees and certain green patches, small or big areas, hold sacredness, considering the abode of divinity, with some believing it to be village deities, serpents, ancestral spirits, and similar divine beings. The Sacred Grove is guided by presiding deities (Deswal, 2024). These places are maintained by indigenous groups, tribes, native religious communities, and in some cases, in Kerala, each of the houses or “*Tharavad*” have a Sacred Grove. It is considered a taboo to fell a tree or even pick anything from such a Sacred Grove with a belief system that it can bring ire of the “Presiding Deity” to the offender or to the whole community or village (Kerala, 2009).

Environmentally, the Sacred Groves are rich in flora and fauna, but are now endangered; the existing ones are only preserved due to their divinity. These are considered the remaining lungs of any place, more particularly in urban areas. The Sacred Groves help in regulating the air, soil formation, purifying air and water, reservoir of rare herbal medicines, among other things (Deswal, 2024).

Culturally, people come together to perform rituals in the Sacred Grove as a part of tradition and culture that fosters community bonding. The community, eventually, preserve the culture, traditions, rituals, or religion which are part of their identity, because of the Sacred Groves (Deswal, 2024).

³ Botanical name “*Ficus religiosa*”

Challenges to maintain Sacred Groves: The imminent threat to the Sacred Groves is the exponential increase in the nuclear family system, loss of religious and spiritual temperament, lack of awareness towards the preservation of the environment, western influence, lack of cultural value, non-integration of the importance of the environment in mainstream education, and several other significant challenges to be explored and studied (Kerala, 2009).

Environmental Litigations: Over the years, laws governing the environment have evolved through environmental litigation, which had a limited scope that can be understood from the earlier judgments on the environment. Initially, environmental jurisprudence started through the Public Interest Litigation (PIL) interpreting the fundamental right implicitly provided under Article 21 (Right to Life) of the Constitution of India, which has paved the way for judicial activism. To mention some of the environmental landmark judgements which marked the beginning of judicial activism and paved the way for ecological justice are J. C. Galstaun v. Dunia Lal Seal (1905)⁴, Rural Litigation and Entitlement Kendra, Dehradun v. State of U.P. & Ors. (1985)⁵, M.C. Mehta v. Union of India (1997)⁶, Vellore Citizen Welfare Forum v. Union of India and Ors. (1996)⁷, T.N. Godavarman Thirumulpad v. Union of India (1997)⁸, T. N. Godavarman Thirumulpad and Ors. v. Union of India and Ors (2022)⁹ (Case, n.d.), and such other several judgements have gradually catalysed to “Ecological Justice”.

Ecological Justice: The term “Ecological Justice”, also called as “interspecies justice” or “ecojustice” by some authors, not only focuses on humans *vis-à-vis* the environment but also non-human beings, giving a holistic approach to live in harmony with nature and bring all living beings allowing distributive ecojustice (Wienhues, 2020).

There are several landmark judgments delivered by the Supreme Court of India; however, it is pertinent to discuss one landmark judgment which spearheaded the movement in protecting the environment, particularly Sacred Groves, viz. T. N. Godavarman Thirumulpad v. Union of India¹⁰ (JJ J.S. Verma, 1996). Through this judgment, the scope of definition of the term “forest land” under Section 2 of the Forest (Conservation) Act, 1980, was further given a clear interpretation, apart from the dictionary meaning, to include, regardless of the ownership

⁴ (1905) 9 CWN 612

⁵ AIR 1982 SC 65

⁶ AIR 1997 SC 734

⁷ (1996) 5 SCC 647

⁸ AIR 1997 SC 1228

⁹ IA (S) 41723 OF 2023 IN W.P. (C) (S) 202 OF 1995

¹⁰ T.N. Godavarman Thirumulpad v. Union of India & Ors. (W.P.(Civil) No. 171/96)

or classification, any area recorded as forest in the Government record (Ministry of Environment & Forest, 2004).

The Supreme Court of India in T. N. Godavarman Thirumalpad¹¹ has interpreted Sacred Grove as patches or clusters of forest or trees that hold profound spiritual or cultural importance for local communities, which sustain and protect them. It further stated that the highest number of Sacred Groves are in India, though their existence is erasing with each passing day. This judgment was the result of the Interlocutory Application with respect to the protection of Sacred Grove or “Orans” as known in Rajasthan, which was also demarcated as “deemed forest”. Rajasthan State Forest Policy, 2010 has provided specifically for the preservation of the Sacred Grove or “Oran” and addressed it as “...religious faith in conservation”, however the Hon’ble Court observed that subsequently, the Rajasthan State Forest Policy, 2023 has omitted that part and generally mentioned for the protection, conservation and plantation of such “Oran” (JJ B. R Gavai, 2024). The Biological Diversity Act, 2002 and the Wildlife Protection Act, 1972, have provided for the protection of community reserves, protect and respect the knowledge of local people, and preserve biodiversity. The Convention on Biological Diversity, 1992, imposes an obligation on the signatory to preserve the indigenous community and preserve the resources with its cultural practices. Even the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNDRIP) and the Rio Declaration on Environment and Development, 2006, recognise and acknowledge the rights and traditional practices of the indigenous community for sustaining the environment. The Forest Rights Act, 2006, emphasises on rights of the community and their duty towards the wildlife, resources and biodiversity. This judgement went ahead and reiterated the importance of the Sacred Grove being the *in situ* preservation of natural forest resources. Further, appreciated the community-driven model named “Piplantri” spearheaded by Shri. Shyam Sundar Paliwal, the Sarpanch of a village from the State of Rajasthan, wherein he created this model to plant 111 trees on the birth of a girl child as a tribute to his deceased daughter. This small initiative has not only nourished the environment with rich flora and fauna but also is fixing the gender disparity and aiding economic growth (JJ B. R Gavai, 2024). The Hon’ble Supreme Court has directed the State of Rajasthan to preserve the Sacred Grove which has been listed therein and further to conduct a survey, include and classify these Sacred Groves as “Forest” based on the cultural and ecological importance and

¹¹ In Re: T. N. Godavarman Thirumalpad v. Union of India & Ors. (I.A. No. 41723 of 2022 in W.P. (C) No. 202 of 1995

not on the size of the Sacred Groves or “*Orans*”. Further, through Section 36 C of the Wildlife Protection Act, 1972, these Sacred Groves were identified as community reserves, to ensure the compliance of the directions for which a committee was formed, thereby fortifying the protection of the Sacred Grove legally.

Additionally, through this judgement, the Hon’ble Supreme Court further suggested empowering communities to protect such Sacred Groves, and emphasised the provisions of the Forest Rights Act, 2006, to identify Sacred Groves as ‘Community Forest Reserve’. It further suggested Central and State Governments encourage and adopt the ‘*Piplantri*’ model¹² and to provide financial assistance and replicate in other States as well, and further recommended the Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change¹³ to create a comprehensive policy for the management and governance of Sacred Groves all across the country (JJ B. R Gavai, 2024). This judgement has comprehensively encapsulated the significance of Sacred Grove and its survey, preservation, protection, and monitoring, thus giving a legal validity and impetus to ecological justice.

Conclusion and Suggestions: This paper is an attempt to understand the Sacred Grove and its cultural significance, sacredness, environmental protection, and the trajectory of recognition and achieving momentum in Ecological Justice.

As this paper has highlighted, the latest T. N. Godavarman¹⁴ judgement has emphasised the protection of “*Oran*” of Rajasthan, thereby highlighting the environmental significance, protection, preservation, and survey of the Sacred Groves across the nation. Although, directions and suggestions besides forming Committees are provided in the judgment, time will reveal the effective implications. The author suggests that the Hon’ble Supreme Court deal with matters of environment in a time-bound manner and strictly fix the schedule of its compliance without any adjournment unless essential, and provide strict directions to the relevant authorities for its implementation. Awareness across all strata of society, and more particularly in children starting from primary class, by developing curiosity and making it mandatory for children to understand the importance and value of living in harmony with nature, by all parents, guardians, caregivers, teachers, and societies in general, which is “*sin qua non*” to preserve and protect culture and ecology. The recent movies, such as the “*Kantara*”

¹² https://nirdpr.org.in/NIRD_Docs/newsletters/Sep20n1.pdf

¹³ <https://moef.gov.in/forest-conservation>

¹⁴ *supra*

series, explore the Sacred Grove or “*Devarakadu*” as known in Karnataka, the Deities associated, its flora and fauna and how it is important to respect and preserve such Sacred Groves. Thus, everyone must realise that humans are just part of the whole ecology and live in harmony with all beings by preserving and protecting the environment. On a philosophical note, it is better to leave the remote Sacred Groves without any deep survey unless any unreported or reported violation.

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